

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Registering Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)

Obtaining unique identifiers for digital objects

Authors: Ellen M. Quardokus (Indiana University)

Approved by: Katy Börner (11/30/2022), Bruce Herr (11/10/2022)

Introduction

Digital object identifiers (DOIs) are used to uniquely identify documents, objects, and other works with a persistent identifier. DOIs are issued by the International Organization for Standardization via a DOI registration agency. HuBMAP uses the DataCite agency. To prepare a digital object and its associated metadata for DOI registration, XML files containing this metadata and a link to the raw data must be generated. The DataCite-metadata-generator can be used to compile the XML file in the DataCite schema via an open-source, customizable online form. This SOP is designed for use by MC-IU personnel who register DOIs for Human Reference Atlas digital objects.

DataCite's REST API (<https://support.datacite.org/docs/api-create-doi>) is used to create DOIs for digital objects included in the Human Reference Atlas. For resources such as 2D or 3D reference models, associated Anatomical Structures, Cell Types plus Biomarkers (ASCT+B) tables, the ontology crosswalk to 2D or 3D reference objects, and Organ Mapping Antibody Panels (OMAPs), resource-specific metadata is captured in an XML file format based on the metadata schema for required fields specified in the DataCite metadata schema (<https://schema.datacite.org>). The DataCite DOI registration process makes it possible to create a Draft DOI, for which the information remains editable and not publicly available. These are then reviewed by the DataCite Registrar (IEC). Upon approval, they are converted to a Findable status DOI (<https://support.datacite.org/docs/api-create-DOIs>).

Registering DOIs using DataCite licenses associated with HuBMAP funding tags these digital objects and DOIs as recognizable and connected to the Human Reference Atlas. These digital objects will be inherited by other major institutions that can ensure their internally consistent publication and usage in the future.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **DOI Contact (IEC)** provides HuBMAP IDs, collects the XML files for digital objects, and assigns DOI registration tasks to the DataCite Registrar (IEC).

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The **DOI Contact (MC-IU)** is responsible for collecting metadata for documents, objects or other works and providing an XML file using the DataCite metadata schema.

The **DataCite Registrar (IEC)** is responsible for using XML files for digital object metadata to register digital object identifiers (DOI) with DataCite. These identifiers are composed of a DataCite license prefix and HuBMAP ID.

The **System Architect (MC-IU)** is responsible for reviewing and approving digital objects uploaded to the CCF releases GitHub repository branch (<https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases>) associated with the impending release.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
DOI Contact (IEC)	Bill Shirey	shirey@pitt.edu
DOI Contact (MC-IU)	Ellen M. Quardokus	ellenmq@indiana.edu
DataCite DOI Registrar (IEC)	Bill Shirey	shirey@pitt.edu
System Architect	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@indiana.edu

Procedures

- The DOI Contact (MC-IU) identifies resources called digital objects (DOs) that should be published with a permanent HuBMAP DOI as part of an HRA release. This is done in consultation with the principal investigator and project manager. Examples of digital objects requiring DOIs include
 - organ-specific ASCT+B tables,
 - 3D reference models stored as GLB files,
 - the crosswalk table that connects ontology IDs for “anatomical structures in the ASCT+B tables” to 3D representation of anatomical structures represented by “scene nodes” in the 3D reference model GLB files,
 - 2D Functional Tissue Unit (FTU) reference models stored as SVG files,
 - 2D FTU crosswalks to ontology Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI) present in ASCT+B tables, and
 - Organ Mapping Antibody Panels (OMAPs).
- Once it is known which digital objects will require DOI registration, the DOI Contact (MC-IU) will make a list of these file names and submit this to the DOI contact (IEC) to obtain a HuBMAP ID for each digital object. The HuBMAP ID will be used to create the DOI for each digital object. The HuBMAP ID is entered into the markdown files for the

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HRA release pages for each digital object and in the XML files used to register the DOI for each digital object.

- The DOI Contact (MC-IU) uploads the digital object files identified for DOI registration to the CCF-releases GitHub repository in a branch containing a folder for the CCF release. Each file is placed into the subfolders for the relevant type of resource.
- CCF-releases GitHub repository: <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases>
 - V1.0 <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases/tree/main/v1.0>
 - V1.1 <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases/tree/main/v1.1>
 - V1.2 <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases/tree/main/v1.2>
 - V1.3 <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases/tree/main/v1.3>
- The file naming convention for GitHub repositories is as follows:
 - Use dashes as delimiters
 - Never use spaces or underscores. Spaces are converted to %20 in URLs or can break a URL when shared. Underscores are difficult to see when the file name is displayed as an underlined link.
 - Use lower case letters as opposed to uppercase letters

The folders needed and their contents are as follows:

Folder name in ccf-release branch	File extension for the file type DOI'd	Description and usage of file type
2d-ftu	.svg .csv	2D functional tissue unit object saved as scalable vector graphic (.svg) file 2D object crosswalk table (.csv)
asct-b	.csv	table based files should be uploaded in comma separated format (i.e. ASCT+B tables, OMAP tables, 3D and 2D object crosswalk tables)
docs	.html	files are needed for the HRA portal, one page per resource

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markdown	.md	Markdown pages for each digital object identifier (DOI) resource used as source page that are called from within the .html pages for HRA Portal
models	.glb	3D reference files plus 3D crosswalk (.csv)
omap	.csv	table based files should be uploaded in comma separated format (i.e. OMAP tables)
xml	.xml	files are needed one per resource to be DOI registered

- A CHANGELOG.md file also exists for each release and lives in each CCF release folder; it lists major changes between CCF-releases.
- Collect metadata for resources that require a DOI to be registered. This can occur while resource files are being collected and uploaded to GitHub CCF-releases.
 - ASCT+B tables: the first 10 rows contain pertinent information on authors and reviewers and their ORCID IDs, organ, resource version.
 - 3D reference object: medical illustrator, 3D organ model reviewers, it is useful to collect this metadata in a google document provided to the MC-IU team members responsible for the CCF release.
 - 2D FTU reference object: medical illustrator, 2D FTU illustrations, reviewers, it is useful to collect this metadata in a google document provided to the MC-IU team members responsible for the HRA release.
- The DOI Contact (MC-IU) collects the specific names of items and the metadata associated with them using the below Google doc. Use this template for collecting metadata. The HRA Portal website developer will need this information to create the landing page within the HRA Portal. Because there is so much information to collect for each resource, the below template has served as a resource for two processes: 1) creating landing pages (Overview page) for each resource on the HRA Portal and 2) registering DOIs for these same digital objects.

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- The empty Google doc template for digital objects metadata and description of scope and coverage is here. It can be filled out directly by authors of the digital object.
 - [CCF_Portal_Info_Template_for_DOI_registration](#)

DOI Formation

DOIs are formed from the DataCite license Invariable DOI field prefix: <https://doi.org/10.48539/> plus the HuBMAP ID, which are obtained from the DOI Registrar (IEC).

XML file creation for each digital object using metadata collected for each

- Creating XML files can be done in many ways with different software tools. You can use an XML editor like Oxygen XML Editor (<https://www.oxygenxml.com>), which is available for IU faculty, students and staff from IUWare (iuware.iu.edu). You can use Microsoft Excel to create XML files: <https://blog.udemy.com/excel-to-xml>. A third method is to use the DataCite Metadata Generator tool. This easy-to-use tool is tailored to generating XML files using a human readable form matching the DataCite Schema for DOI registration.
- To use Excel:
 - Make a copy of the empty XML template found here: <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases/blob/main/v1.0/xml/template.xml>
 - The XML files from v1.0 are stored on GitHub: <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases/tree/main/v1.0/xml>. These files can be used as examples.
- To use the Datacite Metadata Generator:
 - This tool works in a web browser to easily generate a DataCite compatible XML that can be added to the ccf-releases/<currently release branch>.
 - Download the datacite-metadata-generator here: <https://github.com/mpaluch/datacite-metadata-generator>
 - The left side is a customizable, human readable form that automatically generates the corresponding XML code on the right side of the window. XML code can be saved or copied into a GitHub XML file.

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	<p>Plus HuBMAP ID Example: HuBMAP ID = HBM449.NWVK.668 DOI would be https://doi.org/10.48539/HBM449.NWVK.668</p>
TITLE	<p>Contains the title of the digital object. For ASCT+B tables, this corresponds to Row 1 of the top 10 metadata fields called Organ name</p>
CREATORS	<p>These are the authors of the digital object; if there are multiple authors, you add (+) the correct set of metadata fields for each author:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • creator name • given name, family name, • name identifier (used for the ORCID number Ex: 0000-0001-9961-7673) • Name ID Scheme (used to indicate what type of identifier it is (Ex: ORCID)) • Identifier scheme URI (used to provide the web address of orcid Ex: https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9961-7673) • Creator affiliation (optional)
PUBLISHER	HuBMAP
PUBLICATION YEAR	Fill with current year
<p>Resource Type and (Resource type drop down list):</p>	<p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organ Mapping Antibody Panel (OMAP) (Dataset) • 2D FTU reference object (Image) • 3D reference object (Model) • ASCT+B Table (Dataset) • ASCT+B table to 2D FTU mapping Table (Other) • ASCT+B table to 3D model mapping Table (Other)
Recommended fields:	

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Subject	Exact title with version name (Example: OMAP Intestines CODEX table v1.0)
<p>Contributor(s)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ [contributorType] ContactPerson DataCollector DataCurator DataManager Distributor Editor HostingInstitution Producer ProjectLeader ProjectManager ProjectMember RegistrationAgency RegistrationAuthority RelatedPerson Researcher ResearchGroup RightsHolder Sponsor Supervisor WorkPackageLeader Other 	<p>This is the location you must put any other contributors to a digital object. NOTE: "Other" is used for Reviewers because there is no such named contributor. Project leader is used for the project leads for different digital objects. Typically this is the PI who has obtained the funding for the project.</p>
Date(s)	This is the release date of the digital object.
<p>Date type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ [dateType] Accepted Available Copyrighted Collected Created Issued Submitted Updated Valid 	<p>This field is used to qualify what the date means. For HRA digital objects, select "available"</p>

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Description	This field should contain the same description as used for the individual digital object on the HRA portal. (For example, see this escription for the Lung ASCT+B table https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-releases/v1.2/docs/asct-b/lung.html)
Other Elements Fields:	
Language	English
Alternate Identifier(s):	Use this field to enter the alphanumeric HuBMAP ID (Ex: HBM449.NWVK.668)
Alternate ID type	Enter “HuBMAP ID”
Format	Enter the file format. OMAP, ASCT+B = .csv 3D models = .glb 2D FTU illustrations = .svg
Rights List:	Enter the type of licensing for the digital object. We use “Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)”
Rights URI	Enter the associated uniform resource identifier (uri) for the licensing entered in the Rights list. For HRA this is https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0
Funding Reference	For HuBMAP this would be “National Institutes of Health”
Award Number	Enter the award number of the funding of the Project Leader(s)

- Update the reference-entities.tsv file in the CCF-releases main <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases> for the new CCF release; <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases/blob/main/reference-entity-ids.tsv>. This file is a running list of all digital objects from every release for which DOIs have been registered.
- The fields (columns) in the .tsv correspond to the following with an example:

	hubmap_id	landing_page_to_register	data_information_page	doi
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1	HBM963.TBFP.428	https://entity.api.hubmapconsortium.org/redirect/HBM963.TBFP.428	https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-releases/v1.0/docs/asct-b/bone-marrow-and-blood.html	https://doi.org/10.48539/HBM963.TBFP.428
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- The DOI Contact (MC-IU) uploads the XML files to CCF-releases/v1.x
 - Example for v1.0:
<https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases/tree/main/v1.0/xml>
- The DOI Contact (MC-IU) notifies the DOI Contact (IEC) that the XML files are uploaded to CCF releases GitHub repository; however, the preferred method is to make a .zip archive of all the XML files and send it to the DOI Contact (IEC) who will then request that the DataCite Registrar (IEC) perform the DOI registration process at the DataCite DOI registry. Allow a minimum of 2 weeks for the registration process, preferably more. The ability to have active DOIs on the CCF/HRA portal is dependent upon the DOI registration process completion.
- Send one .zip of a folder of XML files, one XML per digital object resource to have DOI registered. This can be easily created using GitHub Desktop.

References

The DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs is located here:

https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.4/doc/DataCite-MetadadataKernel_v4.4.pdf

Datacite metadata schema:

https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.3/doc/DataCite-MetadadataKernel_v4.3.pdf

Metadata XML Example:

<https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.3/example/datacite-example-full-v4.xml>

Example from first set of organs template: Template XML file:

<https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases/blob/main/v1.0/xml/template.xml>

Examples from first set of 3D ref organs (zip file containing XML files)

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Z9bRsSi9_7qy-d1FHom4HTMuAZjfAS0o/view

From crosswalk:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/11R_jU5039V1Zdd2f12waG8qe57GfLtkEtdiaL_6DIlg/e/dit#gid=0

Links to additional examples on this page: <https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.3/>

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Glossary

Comma-separated values (.csv): This is a text file that has a specific format which allows data to be saved in a table structure.

Digital Object Identifier (DOI): A persistent interoperable identifier.

DataCite: A leading global non-profit organization that provides persistent digital object identifiers (DOIs) for research data and other research outputs.

GLB file format: Also called GL Transmission Format Binary file (.glb), this is a 3D file format specification, see <https://docs.fileformat.com/3d/glb/>.

Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG): A web-friendly vector file format (.svg). As opposed to pixel-based raster files like JPEGs, vector files store images via mathematical formulas based on points and lines on a grid.

Uniform Resource Identifier (URI): Identifies a resource and differentiates it from others by using a name, location, or both and contains components like a scheme, authority, path, and query.

Uniform Resource Locator (URL): Identifies the web address or location of a unique resource; however, its authority consists of a domain name and port.

Acknowledgments

The Human Reference Atlas is under active development by the Indiana University Mapping Component as part of the HuBMAP HIVE effort with expert input by the HuBMAP team. Data was provided by the HuBMAP Tissue Mapping Centers. This research has been funded by the NIH Common Fund through the Office of Strategic Coordination/Office of the NIH Director under awards OT2OD033756 and OT2OD026671, by the Cellular Senescence Network (SenNet) Consortium through the Consortium Organization and Data Coordinating Center (CODCC) under award number U24CA268108, by the NIDDK Kidney Precision Medicine Project grant U2CDK114886, and the NIH National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), Department of Health and Human Services under BCBB Support Services Contract HHSN316201300006W/HHSN27200002.